

α -Amino Acid Dithiocarbamate Complexes of Cobalt(II)

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Dithiocarbamate complexes of transition metals have been studied in detail¹. Some dithiocarbamate derivatives of linear α -amino acids and their nickel(II) complexes², dithiocarbamate complexes of branched and cyclic amino acids with nickel(II)³, thermal behaviour of nickel(II) complexes⁴, ir and epr studies of α -amino acid-dithiocarbamate complexes of platinum(II)⁵ have been studied. Dithiocarbamates of a few other α -amino acids have been synthesised and tested for hepatoprotective activity⁶. But α -amino acid dithiocarbamate complexes of the other transition metals have not been studied in detail. These complexes have the coordination sites of amino (N), dithiocarbamate (CS_2^-) and carboxylate (COO^-) and these residues are present in many proteins. Hence these can be tried as models to study the coordination of proteins to metal ions². In this paper, the preparation and characterisation of glycine, DL-alanine, DL-valine and L-leucine dithiocarbamate complexes of cobalt(II) are reported.

Results and Discussion

The results of the elemental analysis of the complexes (Table 1) correspond to a stoichiometry for metal : ligand ratio of 1 : 3. The molecular formula of the complexes could be represented as CoL_3 (L = glycine, DL-alanine, DL-valine, L-leucine dithiocarbamates).

The molar conductances of the complexes in $10^{-3}M$ acetone were in the range $0-10 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$ showing that the complexes are neutral. The room temperature magnetic susceptibility data of the complexes show them to be diamagnetic. This proves that Co^{II} is oxidised to Co^{III} by air during

complexation. This is in agreement with the earlier observations⁷.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd	Analysis % Found/(Calcd)				
	C	H	N	S	Co
Co(glydtcl) ₃	21.7 (21.2)	3.3 (2.4)	8.2 (8.3)	37.1 (37.7)	11.2 (11.6)
Co(DL-aladtcI) ₃	27.0 (26.1)	4.1 (3.3)	7.2 (7.6)	35.0 (34.9)	10.5 (10.7)
Co(DL-valdtcl) ₃	33.9 (34.0)	5.4 (4.7)	6.5 (6.6)	30.1 (30.2)	9.2 (9.3)
Co(L-leudtcI) ₃	37.0 (37.2)	5.4 (5.3)	6.2 (6.2)	28.1 (28.4)	8.6 (8.7)

The established molecular structure of the barium salt of glycinedithiocarbamate² indicated that only S-atoms are coordinated to the metal ions, with the ligand behaving as bidentate².

The ir bands at $1400-1600 cm^{-1}$ (COO^-) in the ligand are absent in all the complexes. The band at $1700-1750 cm^{-1}$ ($C=O$) in the complexes is absent in the ligand. Other bands were observed at $2950-3260$ (OH), $3230-3340$ (NH) and $360 cm^{-1}$ (Co-S)⁸. There is substantial shift in the ν_{C-S} band during complexation. These facts show that complexation takes place through the sulphur atoms and not through the oxygen atom of the carboxylic acid group or through the nitrogen atom. This is also proved by the product of the TG analysis of the complexes in nitrogen atmosphere at 590° , which corresponds to cobalt sulphide indicating the Co-S bond.

In the electronic spectra of the complexes, the bands at $15000-16000$ and $22000-27000 cm^{-1}$ are assigned to ${}^1T_{1g} \leftarrow {}^1A_{1g}$ and ${}^1T_{2g} \leftarrow {}^1A_{1g}$

transitions respectively⁹. These transitions are characteristic of low-spin d^6 -system and prove that Co^{II} has been oxidised by air to Co^{III} during complex formation, since this oxidation state is stabilised by chelation.

Based on these facts, an octahedral skeleton with D_3 symmetry is proposed for the complexes as the complexes belong to the ML_3 chelate species ($\text{L} = \text{glydtcH}$, DL-aladtcH , DL-valdtcH , L-leudtcH)¹⁰.

Experimental

Amino acids (Loba; 99% purity), cobalt(II) chloride hexahydrate (ExcelaR) and other chemicals (AnalaR) were used as such. Water refers to distilled water.

The barium salts of the dithiocarbamates of the amino acids (glycine and DL-alanine) were prepared by the methods reported earlier².

Tris(glycinedithiocarbamato)cobalt(III) : To the amino acid (glycine : 6 g, 0.08 mol) dissolved in water, was added NaOH (4 g, 0.1 mol) and the mixture was stirred to get a clear solution. CS_2 (5.7 ml, 0.09 mol) was then added to it, followed by acetone in small amounts, till CS_2 dissolved fully leaving behind a clear solution. An aqueous solution of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (3.2 g, 0.013 mol) was added dropwise to the above solution (molar ratio 1 : 3) and stirred. The solution immediately turned green showing the formation of the complex. To the green solution, diethyl ether was added followed by dilute HCl (dropwise) and shaken thoroughly. The ether layer was then separated and allowed to evaporate. The resulting green solid complex was purified by redissolving in ether, filtered to remove any undissolved portion and again evaporated. This complex is represented as $\text{Co}(\text{glydtcH})_3$.

Tris(DL-alaninedithiocarbamato)cobalt(III) : It was prepared from DL-alanine (6 g, 0.07 mol), NaOH (3 g, 0.08 mol), CS_2 (4.8 ml, 0.08 mol) and $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2.9 g, 0.012 mol) as above. This complex is represented as $\text{Co}(\text{DL-aladtcH})_3$.

Tris(DL-valinedithiocarbamato)cobalt(III) : It was prepared from DL-valine (6 g, 0.05 mol), NaOH (2.3 g, 0.06 mol), CS_2 (3.7 ml, 0.06 mol) and $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2.5 g, 0.01 mol) as above. This complex

is represented as $\text{Co}(\text{DL-valdtcH})_3$.

Tris(L-leucinedithiocarbamato)cobalt(III) : It was prepared from L-leucine (6 g, 0.05 mol), NaOH (2.2 g, 0.05 mol), CS_2 (3.3 ml, 0.055 mol) and $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2.34 g, 0.0098 mol) as above. This complex is represented as $\text{Co}(\text{L-leudtcH})_3$. C, H and N analyses were carried out by a Heraeus-Varlo-Erba 1108 instrument at R.S.I.C., Lucknow. Sulphur¹¹ was estimated by precipitating it as BaSO_4 and cobalt¹² colorimetrically. TG analysis was carried out in nitrogen atmosphere at a heating rate of 10°min^{-1} . Magnetic susceptibility was measured at room temperature using a Gouy balance, EM 50 type of control systems. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded in a Pye-Unicam SP 2000 and PE 983 instruments, electronic spectra (methanol) on a AMINCO DR-2a spectrophotometer and diffuse reflectance spectra (solid state) on a Varian-Cary 2390 spectrophotometer. The molar conductance was measured in acetone using a Philips dip-type conductivity cell and an Elico CM 82 T conductivity bridge.

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